

Experimental

3-Amino-2-sub-imtdazo (1, 2-a)-pyridines :

Aldehyde bisulphite addition product (0.1 M) was added to 2-aminopyridine (0.1 M, 9.4 g) in water (60 ml) and heated on a waterbath for 2 hrs, filtered, cooled (30°), KCN (0.1 M, 6.5 g) in water added and stirred for 5 hrs. It was extracted with CHCl₃ (3 × 50 ml), CHCl₃ extract dried over Na₂SO₄ and the solvent distilled off at reduced pressure. The residue was treated with petroleum ether and crystallised from ethanol (95%) (Table 1).

Preparation of Schiff bases :

3-Amino-2-phenyl-imidazo (1, 2-a)-pyridine and aldehydes in equimolar proportion were refluxed in alcohol for 2 hrs. The anils separated on cooling. They were filtered, dried and crystallised from ethanol (95%) (Table 2).

3-Arylidine amino-2-phenyl-imidazo (1, 2-a)-pyridines

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On Glucosyl Thioureides: Preparation of Certain S-Tetra-O-Acetyl-D-Glucopyranosyl Aryl Isothiocarbamides

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THE pharmacological and biochemical aspects of alkyl/aryl ureides, -thioureides and -guanidines have been very extensively investigated and many compounds of this series have been described in the literature¹. They have been found to possess marked biological activities and are used as bacteriostatic agents and diuretic, analgesic, antithyroid drugs. A very few thioglucosides of thiocarbamides are reported to date¹. In the present communication seven S-tetra-O-acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl aryl isothiocarbamides have been reported. These were prepared by the interaction of tetra-O-

acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl bromide (I) and aryl thiocarbamides (II).

(I)

Ac=Acetyl

Isopropanolic solution of tetra-O-acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl bromide (0.04 M, 16 g in 25 ml) was mixed with a suspension of phenyl thiocarbamide (0.04 M, 6 g in 25 ml isopropanol) and the mixture after shaking for about ten mins was warmed over a hot water bath at 70° until a clear solution was obtained. The clear solution was then kept at room temperature for 18 hrs. It was mixed with water when a small quantity of semi solid was obtained. The aqueous layer was separated. This aqueous solution was acidic and non-desulphurisable when boiled with alkaline plumbite solution. When treated with aqueous picric acid, it afforded a picrate, m.p. 155°. All these clearly indicated the presence of S-tetra-O-acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl phenyl isothiocarbamide hydrobromide in aqueous solution.

The aqueous solution when made basic with NH₄OH, afforded a sticky mass which solidified on standing for several hours and crystallized from ethanol, m.p. 138°. It gave Molisch test and was non-desulphurisable when boiled with alkaline plumbite solution. It gave a picrate, m.p. 155°, when warm ethanolic solution of it was treated with ethanolic picric acid. Its specific rotation was $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 5.86^\circ$ (C, 2.2 in CHCl₃). The ir spectrum clearly indicated the presence of ν_{NH} 3410 cm⁻¹, $\nu_{C=O}$ 1720 cm⁻¹, $\nu_{C=N}$ 1650 cm⁻¹ and ν_{C-S} 750 cm⁻¹ bands^{4,5}. All these clearly indicated the product as S-tetra-O-acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl phenyl isothiocarbamides (IIIa).

When the interaction of tetra-O-acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl bromide was extended to other aryl thiocarbamides the related S-tetra-O-acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl aryl isothiocarbamides (IIIb-IIIg) were isolated. All these products afforded picrates and have been listed in Table 1.

where, R=(a) Phenyl, (b) o-Tolyl, (c) m-Tolyl, (d) p-Tolyl, (e) o-Cl-Phenyl, (f) m-Cl-Phenyl and (g) p-Cl-Phenyl

TAG=Tetra-O-acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl.

TABLE 1 - INTERACTION OF TETRA-O-ACETYL-D-GLUCOPYRANOSYL BROMIDE (0.04 M) AND ARYL THIOCARBAMIDE (0.04 M) IN ISOPROPANOL

Sl. No.	Aryl thiocarbamide (g)	S-tetra-O-acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl aryl isothiocarbamide m. p. °C yield (g)	Analysis %		$[\alpha]_D^{20}$ in CHCl ₃	λ_{max} (nm)	log ϵ_{max}	m. p. °C	Picrate Analysis %	
			Found	Calcd.					Found	Calcd.
1.	-Phenyl (6.0)	-Phenyl (IIIa) 138, (5.0)	N, 5.58 S, 6.54	N, 5.80 S, 6.39	+5.86° (c 2.2134)	244	(4.9354)	155	N, 9.51 S, 5.0	N, 9.84 S, 4.51
2.	-o-Tolyl (6.6)	-o-Tolyl (IIb) 135, (6.0)	N, 5.55 S, 6.28	N, 5.64 S, 6.45	-3.39° (c 2.359)	245	(4.0228)	145	N, 9.29 S, 5.23	N, 9.65 S, 4.41
3.	-m-Tolyl (6.6)	-m-Tolyl (IIIc) 133, (5.5)	N, 5.26 S, 6.95	N, 5.64 S, 6.45	+8.16° (c 1.975)	245	(4.5588)	129	N, 9.58 S, 4.74	N, 9.65 S, 4.41
4.	-p-Tolyl (6.6)	-p-Tolyl (IIId) 123, (2.0)	N, 5.58 S, 6.79	N, 5.64 S, 6.45	+1.82° (c 3.3796)	245.5	(3.8858)	152	N, 9.19 S, 3.65	N, 9.65 S, 4.41
5.	-o-Cl-Phenyl (7.4)	-o-Cl-Phenyl (IIIe) 136, (3.5)	N, 5.30 S, 6.13	N, 5.42 S, 6.19	-13.58° (c 4.4266)	243.5	(4.9434)	147	N, 7.98 S, 3.84	N, 9.39 S, 4.29
6.	-m-Cl-Phenyl (7.4)	-m-Cl-Phenyl (III f) 151, (3.0)	N, 5.50 S, 6.34	N, 5.42 S, 6.19	+4.55° (c 3.057)	243.5	(4.972)	141	N, 8.06 S, 5.77	N, 9.39 S, 4.29
7.	-p-Cl-Phenyl (7.4)	-p-Cl-Phenyl (III g) 128, (2.4)	N, 5.50 S, 6.87	N, 5.42 S, 6.19	+1.59° (c 4.0288)	243.5	(4.8948)	135	N, 8.35 S, 4.62	N, 9.39 S, 4.29

Satisfactory C, H analysis were obtained for all compounds.

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On Glucosyl Thioureides. Part II. Preparation of 2-S-tetra-O-Acetyl-D-Glucopyranosyl-1,5-Disubstituted-2,4-Isodithiobiurets and 1,5-Disubstituted-2-Isothiobiurets

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RECENTLY, we reported a method for preparation of several S-tetra-O-acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl aryl isothiocarbamides by the interaction of tetra-O-acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl bromide and aryl thiocarbamides^{1,2}. It was considered interesting to study the chemistry of these glucosyl aryl isothiocarbamides with special reference to their reaction with aryl isothiocya-

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nate and aryl isocyanates. The findings are presented in this note.

Reaction of S-tetra-O-acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl phenyl isothiocarbamide and phenyl isothiocyanate in boiling acetone medium gives a clear solution. On mixing the acetone solution with petroleum ether, an oily liquid separates which on triturations several times with petroleum ether gives a granular solid, crystallized from ethanol, m.p. 122°. The product is desulphurisable when boiled with alkaline plumbite solution. On thermal decomposition the smell of phenylisothiocyanate is perceptible. The product has specific rotation², $[\alpha]_D^{25}$, +4.96 (chloroform, c 3.5384) and λ_{max} 246 nm (log ϵ_{max} 5.0799)⁴. The ir spectrum of the product indicates the presence of ν_{NH} (3310 cm⁻¹), $\nu_{C=O}$ (1740 cm⁻¹), $\nu_{C=N}$ (1600 cm⁻¹) $\nu_{C=S}$ (1040 cm⁻¹) and ν_{C-S} (750 cm⁻¹) bands^{4,5}. The product with m.p. 122° has therefore, been assigned the structure 2-S-tetra-O-acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl-1,5-diphenyl-2,4-isodithiobiuret (Ia).

The other S-tetra-O-acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl aryl isothiocarbamides² also on reaction with phenyl isothiocyanate under identical conditions afford the related 2-S-tetra-O-acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl-1-aryl-5-phenyl-2,4-isodithiobiurets (Ib-Ig) (Table 1).

Similarly, the reaction of tetra-O-acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl phenyl isothiocarbamide and phenyl isocyanate in cold benzene medium affords a product, crystallized from ethanol m.p. 159°. This has been assigned the structure 2-S-tetra-O-acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl-1,5-diphenyl-2-isothiobiuret (IIa) on the basis of following facts:

The product is non-desulphurisable when boiled with alkaline plumbite solution. On thermal decomposition